

Appendix A: Build Instructions

ALL-SAFE Laparoscopic Box Trainer

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Materials Required for Assembly:

- 6 sheets of cardboard (minimum 14" x 8.5" or 355mm x 215mm)
- Rubber bands (5 large, or up to 15 smaller, ideally approximately 3mm thick)
- Ruler
- Pencil/writing utensil
- Box cutter/utility knife (adequate for most cuts)
- Scalpel, #11 (not required, but ideal for small/shorter cuts)
- Tape
- Pins (straight or sewing), if possible

Preparation Instructions:

For all of the following steps, you may print each Part (Parts A, B, C, D, E) on 5 11-3/4" x 16-1/2" (297 x 420 mm) pieces of A3 sized paper and use straight pins to secure onto the pieces of cardboard, and use a scalpel and a ruler or straight edge to cut over the template before assembly. *This is especially helpful for Part E.* Alternatively, you can simply use the templates as a measurement guide and assemble as described below.

Part A (make 2 pieces)

- Use a pencil/writing utensil and ruler to draw the Part A measurements on 8.5" x 14" (215mm x 355mm) sheet of cardboard
- Use a box cutter to cut out the general shape of Part A and the light source window
- Use a scalpel or utility knife to cut out the thin, angled slit of Part A

Part B

- Use a pencil and ruler to draw the Part B measurements on 8.5" x 14" (215mm x 355mm) sheet of cardboard
- Use a box cutter to cut out the general shape of Part B
- Use a scalpel to cut out the thin, slit of Part B
- Use a scalpel to cut out the small holes of Part B

- Stab the scalpel through the cardboard and then rotate to make a circle cutout

Preparation instructions, continued

Part B, continued

- Loop 3 rubber bands (more as needed) together to form a strand and thread the strand through both holes
- Tie the rubber band strand together using a normal knot

Preparation instructions, continued

Part C

- Prepare an 8.5"x14" (355mm x 215mm) sheet of cardboard using dimensions supplied on Part C template

Part D

- Use a pencil and ruler to draw the Part D measurements on 8.5" x 14" (355mm x 215mm) sheet of cardboard
 - Use a box cutter to cut out the general shape of Part D
 - Use a scalpel to cut out the thin, slit of Part D
- Note:* an optional rectangular cutout could be added in the center of Part D to serve as an additional light source, if ambient light is low.

Part E

Given the complexity of Part E, you might find it helpful to print Part E template on a 5 11-3/4" x 16-1/2" (297 x 420 mm) piece of A3 sized paper, use straight pins to secure it onto a piece of cardboard, and use a scalpel and a ruler or straight edge to cut over the template before assembly. Alternatively, follow directions below.

- Use a pencil and ruler to draw the Part E measurements on 8.5" x 14" (215mm x 355mm) sheet of cardboard

- Use a box cutter to cut out the shape of Part E

Preparation instructions, continued

Part E, continued

- Use a scalpel (or utility knife) to cut out the laparoscopic tool holes, the middle slot, and the top rectangular cutouts (2 sets of holes have been placed in the template for your convenience (The inner set will likely suffice for most trainees, while outer set might be best for trainees with a wider natural stance)
- Loop two rubber bands (more, if smaller) together and hook one rubber band in the top rectangular cutouts

Assembly Instructions:

- Use tape to attach the two Part A pieces to Part C
 - The Part A pieces will form the sides of the box trainer while the Part C piece will form the back wall
 - Make sure both Part A pieces are assembled on the inside of Part C
 - Tape both the outside and inside corner

Assembly instructions, continued

- Place Part E into the corresponding slits in Part B and Part D
 - Part E forms the angled work surface, while Part B is the front wall of the box trainer and Part D is the top

- Place the side tabs of Part E into the corresponding angled slits in both Part A pieces

- Use tape to attach Part D to both Part A pieces and Part C
 - Part D sits on top/outside of both Part A pieces and Part C

- Use tape to attach Part B to both Part A pieces
 - Make sure both Part A pieces are attached to the inside of Part B

Final Product: The ALL-SAFE Laparoscopic Box Trainer

Internet/Video Conferencing Setup Instructions

- Load the select video conferencing app (e.g. Zoom) on the smartphone and on a corresponding computer/tablet
- Make sure the restricted rotation option is off on the smartphone
- Start the video conferencing app “meeting” on the smartphone and send an invitation to an email accessible on the corresponding computer/tablet
- Open the “meeting” link from the email
 - The computer/tablet will simulate the laparoscope monitor

Acquiring the Proper View

- For a zero degree (0°) view, place the smartphone on Part E so that the screen faces you and the camera points into the rectangular cutout
 - The phone will rest against the top lip of Part B
 - Adjust the smartphone position and/or the training object in the box until the proper view is acquired

Acquiring the Proper View, continued

- For a 30 degree (30°) view, stretch the free rubber band hanging from the top of Part E around the smartphone in the vertical direction (you may connect multiple smaller rubber bands to do this, as needed).

- Lower the smartphone into the rectangular cutout in Part E
- Use the rubber bands attached to Part B to secure the smartphone
- Adjust the smartphone position and/or the training object in the box until the proper view is acquired

Note: Templates are not to scale.

Part A

Part B

Part D

Part E

Appendix B: ALL-SAFE Ectopic Pregnancy Task Trainer

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Materials Required for Assembly:

- 2 large cotton socks
- Plastic wrap
- Fabric glue or stapler
- Penrose drain
- Flour
- Nescafe or food coloring
- Salt
- Toomey Syringe
- Suture tie

Preparation Instructions:

Part A - Uterus

- Take one large sock, stuffing the toe with cotton material (Stuffing can be a matched sock, fabric or lap pad based on availability of materials). This will form the “fundus” of the uterus.
- Narrow the foot of the sock by folding the ends over and securing into place with glue or staples to form the body of the uterus.
- Trim any excess sock material.

Preparation instructions, continued

Part B – Ovaries

- Take small (approximately 5x5 cm) squares of cotton fabric and fold into a round ball.
- Secure ends with staples or glue.

Part C – Ectopic Contents

- Note – you may use playdough if available (bright colors will be more visible)
- If not available, Make home-made dough with the following recipe.
 - Flour – ½ cup
 - Salt – 1/8 cup
 - Nescafe- 1/8 cup
 - Water – ¼ cup
- Mix dry ingredients.
- Add water, mixing thoroughly.
- Mixture should form a soft ball. If too soft or hard, add flour or water, respectively.

Part D – Fallopian tubes with Ectopic Pregnancy

- Take the Penrose drain, securing a suture tie approximately 1/3 of the way along one end.
- Fill a Toomey syringe with dough filling approx. 5-10 cc into the drain, until “ectopic pregnancy” is appropriate size.
- Tie a second tie to keep the dough in place.
- Using a marker or pen, place a single circular mark at the superior side of the ectopic pregnancy. This mark will be used later when practicing intracorporal suturing and knot tying skills.
- Cut 3-4 approximately 1 cm slits in ends of drain to form fimbriae.

Assembly Instructions:

- Secure tubes to uterus.
 - Using a stapler or fabric glue, secure the center of the Penrose drain to the fundus of the constructed uterus, so that each half is clearly visible to either side.

- Use plastic wrap to form mesosalpinx.
 - Place uterus, tubes, and ovaries onto a sheet of plastic wrap in appropriate anatomic positioning.
 - Press second sheet of plastic wrap on top.
 - Trim to appropriate size.

Appendix C: Supply List

Materials	Specifications
<i>Box Trainer</i>	
Cardboard	–
Rubber bands	5 large or 15 small
Ruler	Needs cm/mm markings
Pencil	–
Box Cutter/Utility Knife	–
Tape Pins	Straight or Sewing acceptable
Cell Phone	Video Capability needed
Computer	Minimum of single core 1Ghz or 4 Gb of RAM
WiFi Connection	Bluetooth connection alternative acceptable

<i>Ectopic Pregnancy Task Trainer</i>	
Large Sock	Cotton preferred
Plastic food Wrap	e.g. Saran Wrap or Press ‘N Seal
Fabric Glue	Alternative stapler
Surgical Drain	¾ inch Penrose preferred
Playdough	
Toomey Syringe	

<i>Surgical Instruments & Disposables</i>	
Laparoscopic Needle Driver	
Laparoscopic Blunt Grasper	e.g. Bullnose
Laparoscopic Maryland Grasper	
Trocars x 2	Bladeless > 8 mm preferred. e.g. Medtronic, Ethicon
Silk 2-0 with ½ inch taper needle	e.g. SH needle (Ethicon), V-20 (Covidien)
Suture Ties	Silk preferred